

Determination of ozone (O₃) concentrations by a passive method: A laboratory protocol for students in environmental engineering and related fields

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1. General overview

The measurement of atmospheric pollutant concentrations can be performed using different approaches. The most commonly employed method consists of continuous monitoring at fixed stations integrated into air quality monitoring networks. Other approaches involve successive measurements at different locations within a defined grid over a specified period of time.

Measurements may be manual or automatic. In manual methods, air samples are collected or pollutants are trapped in reactive solutions or filters, followed by laboratory analysis of the collected samples, solutions, or filters. In automatic methods, both sampling and analysis are carried out directly on site by the monitoring equipment.

Measurements can also be classified as continuous or discontinuous. In continuous monitoring, analyses are performed either in real time or after a short sampling interval, depending on the selected integration time. In discontinuous monitoring, analyses are carried out after a relatively long sampling period. For practical reasons, continuous monitoring is generally associated with automatic methods.

The choice between manual or automatic, and continuous or discontinuous monitoring depends on the characteristics of the monitoring equipment, the pollutants of interest — and consequently the mechanisms through which they exert harmful effects — as well as emission conditions and the magnitude and frequency of pollution episodes or peak concentrations.

1.1. Passive sampling method

1.1.1 – Brief introduction

The method was initially developed for occupational hygiene sampling and was subsequently applied in indoor air quality assessment campaigns.

For ozone (O₃) analysis, passive diffusion tubes are commonly used. These samplers consist of a cylindrical body made of glass or Teflon, typically with dimensions of 49 ± 0.05 mm in length and 9 ± 0.05 mm internal diameter. Passive sampling is based on molecular diffusion: ozone enters the tube along a concentration gradient and is subsequently absorbed by a reactive medium located at the closed end of the sampler. After exposure, the collected analyte is quantified in the laboratory, allowing the determination of time-averaged pollutant concentrations.

The ends of the tube are machined to ensure tight fitting of the caps, thereby sealing the sampler on both sides. At one end of the tube, three quartz microfiber filters are placed inside the cap. These filters are impregnated with a specific absorbing reagent, 1,2-di-(4-pyridyl) ethylene (DPE), which reacts selectively with ozone to form a stable reaction product that can subsequently be quantified by spectrophotometric analysis.

For O₃ monitoring, the typical exposure period of the diffusion tubes ranges from approximately 5 to 7 days, although it may be extended to up to two weeks under low ozone concentration conditions.

1.1.2 - Principle of operation for O₃ determination

Passive diffusion tubes operate according to the principle of molecular diffusion, whereby gas molecules migrate from a region of higher concentration (the open end of the tube) to a region of lower concentration (the closed end containing the absorbing medium). This process is described by Fick's first law of diffusion, which states that the diffusive flux is proportional to the concentration gradient, while the amount of analyte collected is inversely proportional to the diffusion path length inside the tube.

$$F_1 = -D_{12} \frac{dC}{dZ} \quad (\text{Eq. 1})$$

where:

- $F_1 \rightarrow$ Pollutant 1 gas flow ($\text{mol cm}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$)
- $D_{12} \rightarrow$ Diffusion coefficient of gas 1 in gas 2 ($\text{cm}^2 \text{s}^{-1}$);
for O_3 at $25^\circ\text{C} \Rightarrow D_{12} = 0.150 \text{ cm}^2 \text{s}^{-1}$ (Fischer, 1981)
- $C \rightarrow$ Concentration of gas 1 in gas 2 (mol.cm^{-3})
- $Z \rightarrow$ Diffusion length (cm)

For a tube with a cross-sectional area of πr^2 (cm^2) and length Z (cm), with a concentration gradient of $C_1 - C_0$ ($\text{molecules} \cdot \text{cm}^{-3}$), the amount Q (moles) of gas transferred along the tube over t seconds is given by:

$$Q = F_1(\pi r^2)t$$

$$Q = -D_{12}(C_1 - C_0)(\pi r^2) \frac{t}{Z} \quad (\text{Eq. 2 e 3})$$

When an effective absorbing medium is used to remove the target gas, the concentration C_0 will be zero, so Q will be negative. However, the negative sign can be ignored, as it only indicates that the flux occurs from regions of higher concentration to regions of lower concentration of gas 1. This method therefore allows the determination of the average concentration of the pollutant (gas 1) in ambient air over a given sampling period, as expressed by the following equation:

$$C = \frac{QZ}{D_{12}\pi r^2 t} \quad (\text{Eq. 4})$$

1.1.3 - Advantages and disadvantages of the method

The advantages and disadvantages of using this type of method for pollutant measurement, in this case O_3 , are summarized in Table 1.

Table 1- Main advantages and disadvantages of using diffusion tubes.

	ADVANTAGES	DISADVANTAGES
DIFFUSION TUBES	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Useful for studying air quality at a regional or local scale; • Small, lightweight, reusable, silent, and relatively inexpensive given their efficiency; • Do not require regular calibration; • Sampling does not depend on any external power source. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Do not provide real-time data; they only yield an average concentration over the exposure period; • Method has a significant absolute margin of error; • Highly susceptible to errors.

1.2 - Preparation of diffusion tubes for O₃

Teflon tubes are used because the material is inert to ozone and slightly opaque, which is advantageous since O₃ is sensitive to ultraviolet radiation and can undergo photochemical reactions.

The tubes have an internal diameter of 9 mm and a length of approximately 53 mm, and were cut in accordance with the specifications provided in various commercial catalogues. The caps, made of white Teflon, were machined to a diameter that ensures a snug fit on the tubes.

Quartz microfiber filters (from Whatman or Pall) were used, punched with a steel die to match the internal diameter of the caps.

A more detailed description of the individual steps involved in passive sampling is provided below; the complete protocol can be found in Annex 1.

1.3 - Impregnation of filters for ozone sampling

The impregnation procedure consists of placing three filters inside one of the caps and impregnating them with a solution of 1,2-di-(4-pyridyl)ethylene (DPE), which contains acetic acid and ethylene glycol in addition to the DPE itself.

Given that both the organic molecules, the DPE, and the complex formed between DPE and ozone are sensitive to radiation and can even be destabilized under intense light, there is a potential for overestimation of concentrations. To minimize this effect, both the caps and the tubes are made opaque.

The literature also reports that sampling is sensitive to increases in air humidity and temperature; in particular, higher ambient temperatures can reduce the efficiency of the passive sampler. One possible explanation is that acetic acid (used in the DPE impregnation solution) can dry out on the glass fiber filters, which is why ethylene glycol is added to prevent the solution from completely drying out.

Immediately after impregnation, the cap - appropriately marked (usually with the letter "O") - is placed on the tube, which is already sealed at the opposite end. The marking on the cap containing the filters serves only as a reference, indicating the correct orientation of the tubes during sampling.

Figure 1 – Schematic representation of the operating principles of diffusion tubes for O₃.

In most cases, the impregnation is carried out on the same day the tubes are exposed, in order to minimize possible contamination. However, when this is not possible, the already impregnated tubes are stored in the laboratory refrigerator, wrapped in aluminum foil, inside a properly sealed box. In addition to impregnating the tubes to be exposed, six blank tubes are also impregnated. These are stored in the refrigerator properly conditioned, during the sampling time of the others, and subsequently all are analyzed together.

It is recommended to use 3 replicate tubes per location. Keep one blank for every 10 locations. The blank can be placed in the shelter, together with the 3 sampling replicate tubes, but the cap is not removed. It remains closed during the entire sampling period.

1.4 – Extraction and analysis

After exposure, the tubes are removed and transported to the laboratory to proceed with their extraction/analysis.

Once in the laboratory, the filters are removed from the tubes, with the aid of a needle, into 6 mL amber vials, and a certain quantity of 3-methyl-2-benzothiazolinone hydrazone hydrochloride (MTBH) is added to them. After the addition of MTBH, the vials are shaken on a mechanical shaker and then left to rest for at least one hour so that the reaction can be

completed. That is, the impregnating DPE reacts with ozone, forming an ozonide, which upon cleavage produces pyridine-4-aldehyde. This, in turn, reacts with MTBH, resulting in a yellow azide.

Subsequently, the samples are transferred to centrifuge tubes and centrifuged so that the filters dissolve and sediment, thereby preventing interference from the fibers in the analytical determination. The next step consists of measuring the absorbance of each sample in a spectrophotometer at 430 nm, with the instrument's zero being set using ultra-pure water.

To finalize the procedure and obtain the calibration curve, a series of standards are prepared from a fresh solution of 4-pyridylaldehyde. After reacting for one hour, their absorbance is also measured at 430 nm.

Note: When designing the calibration curve, the fact that the reaction is not stoichiometric must be taken into account, as 1 mg of 4-pyridylaldehyde corresponds to 0.224 mg of ozone.

2. Data treatment

As previously mentioned, three sampling tubes and one blank are placed in each holder. Therefore, the average ozone concentration in each holder and for each exposure period is calculated as the average of the concentrations of the three replicates, after correction for the blank value. That is, a global blank is calculated (the average of the concentrations of all the blanks from the various holders), and the resulting average concentration of these blanks is subtracted from the average concentration calculated for each holder.

At each sampling point, the standard deviation referring to the concentrations of the three replicates and the associated error are also calculated, with the latter being computed as the quotient between the standard deviation and the mean.

Variability is sometimes observed among the three replicates at each point, and in order to determine whether or not to exclude a specific value, a statistical test - the Dixon's Q test - is applied. For the application of the test, the values are arranged in descending order, and the Q value is calculated as the difference between the value considered an outlier and the value closest to it, divided by the range of the values (difference between the largest and smallest value). Thus,

$$Q_{\text{calculated}} = \frac{\text{Outlier value} - \text{Closest value}}{\text{Amplitude}} \quad (\text{Eq. 5})$$

The rejection or acceptance of a given value is determined by comparing the calculated Q with the tabulated Q. If the calculated Q is greater than or equal to the tabulated Q, the value in question is rejected, with a predefined confidence level (90%, 95%, or 99%). In this study, the Q test is applied to 3 observations (n=3) with a confidence level of 95%, for which the corresponding tabulated value is 0.970, as shown in the table below.

Table 2 – Critical Values for Dixon's Q Test

Rule: Reject the outlier if $Q_{\text{exp}} > Q_{\text{crit}}$

Number of Observations (n)	90% Confidence	95% Confidence	99% Confidence
3	0.941	0.970	0.994
4	0.765	0.829	0.926
5	0.642	0.710	0.821
6	0.560	0.625	0.764
7	0.507	0.568	0.680
8	0.468	0.526	0.634

ANNEX 1 – EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

◆ MATERIALS

- Diffusion tubes
- Quartz microfiber filters from *Whatman* or *Pall*
- Aluminum foil
- Acrylic holders
- Calibrated watch glasses
- Needle
- Tweezers
- 10 mL volumetric flasks
- 25 mL volumetric flasks
- 1,000 mL volumetric flasks
- 6 mL amber glass vials
- 50 μ L and 100 μ L micropipettes
- 1 mL, 2 mL, 5 mL, and 10 mL volumetric pipettes
- 0.5 mL and 5 mL graduated pipettes
- Pasteur pipette
- 1 L glass bottle for storing the MTBH solution
- Centrifuge tubes
- Centrifuge tube rack
- Marker
- Labels

◆ EQUIPMENT

- Refrigerator
- Balance
- Oven
- Mechanical stirring plate
- Centrifuge
- Spectrophotometer

◆ REAGENTS

- 1,2-Di-(4-pyridyl)ethylene (DPE)
- Acetic acid
- Ethylene glycol
- 3-Methyl-2-benzothiazolinone hydrazone hydrochloride (MTBH)
- Concentrated sulfuric acid
- 4-Pyridylaldehyde
- Ultrapure water
- Distilled water

◆ SOLUTIONS

◆ DPE impregnation solution:

- Weigh 0.25 grams of DPE.
- Transfer to a 25 mL flask and make up the volume with acetic acid.
- Add 1 mL of ethylene glycol.

◆ MTBH extraction solution:

- Dissolve 5 grams of MTBH in one liter of ultrapure water (in a 1,000 mL flask).
- Add 5 mL of concentrated sulfuric acid.

Note: The solution is stable for at least one month when stored in the dark. Therefore:

- Transfer the prepared MTBH solution to a 1 L glass bottle.
- Wrap the bottle in aluminum foil.
- Label it and store it in the refrigerator.

◆ 4-Pyridylaldehyde standard solution:

- Dissolve 100 μ L (112.2 mg at 20 °C) of 4-pyridylaldehyde in one liter of distilled water (in a 1,000 mL flask).
- This solution must be freshly prepared each time an analysis is performed.

◆ PROCEDURES

◆ Filter impregnation:

- Place 3 filters on one of the caps of each tube using tweezers, with the rough side facing up.
- Add 50 μ L of the DPE solution using a micropipette.
- Immediately place the cap on the tube, which is already closed at the other end.
- Store in the refrigerator, wrapped in aluminum foil and inside a box, until exposure.

◆ Sample extraction:

- Remove the filter using a needle and transfer it to a 6 mL amber glass vial.
- Add 5 mL of extraction solution to each vial.
- Shake well, preferably using a mechanical stirring plate, for a few minutes.
- Wait at least 1 hour to allow the reaction to complete.
- Transfer the solution to a centrifuge tube.
- Centrifuge at 3,000 RPM for 5 minutes.
- Measure the absorbance at 430 nm against ultrapure water, transferring the sample to the cuvette with a Pasteur pipette.

Note: If the sample is outside the linear range, dilute by adding MTBH solution; do not use water, as it can alter the pH and interfere with the analysis.

◇ **Calibration curve:**

- For 10 mL flasks, transfer the following volumes of the 4-pyridylaldehyde solution: 10.0 mL, 5.0 mL, 2.0 mL, 1.0 mL, and 0.0 mL.
- Make up to the mark with ultrapure water.
- Transfer 0.5 mL of each solution into a 6 mL amber vial, together with 4.5 mL of the MTBH solution.
- Wait 1 hour and measure the absorbance at 430 nm.
- Plot the calibration curve of μg of O_3 versus absorbance, noting that 1 μg of 4-pyridylaldehyde is equivalent to 0.224 μg of O_3 .